

Comparing Similarities and Differences in Learning and Entertainment Needs of High School Students in Hanoi with High School Students of the H'Mong Ethnic Group

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Abstract

High schools are a special part of the education system, where they are responsible for educating and training students between the ages of 15 and 18. These students have special learning and entertainment needs, which depend greatly on the surrounding environment. This article, in addition to research, also conducts surveys to compare the similarities and differences in the learning and entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi with high school students of the H'Mong ethnic group, thereby proposing some ideas for schools and families to promote learning needs and satisfy entertainment needs for these high school students.

Keywords: *Comparison, similarities and differences, learning and entertainment needs, high school students, H'Mong people.*

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Introduction

Education has been and is an important issue in Vietnam. There are more and more changes in the form of assessment of high school students, including the 2018 general education program (with some amendments) applied to junior high school and high school levels or changes in the plan for organizing exams and considering graduation recognition from 2025, aiming to help students master knowledge, apply learned skills to life and have orientation for the future (xaydungchinhsach.chinhphu.vn, 2023). In particular, in addition to the need to study, the right to be nurtured and to play and entertain of students is always protected by the Party and State of Vietnam (baomoi.com, 2024). This shows that education and the protection of students' right to play are increasingly being focused on.

Education today is aimed at students of all levels. High school students are also known as adolescents, which is a stage of development that begins at puberty and ends at adulthood. Adolescence is from 15 to 25 years old, divided into 2 periods:

+ The period from 15 to 18 years old: called early adolescence

+ Period from 18 to 25 years old: called young adulthood

Adolescence also shows the complex and multifaceted nature of the phenomenon, which is limited to two aspects: physiology and psychology. This is a difficult and complicated problem because the rhythm and stages of psychophysiological development do not always coincide with the periods of social

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maturity. This means that physical maturity, intellectual personality, and labor capacity will not coincide with the development time of the age group (Hanoi National University of Education, 2023)

In today's era, labor and social activities are increasingly complex, and children's study time is prolonged, making true social maturity come more slowly. Children's learning needs and entertainment needs are also relatively different.

According to reports, high school students face many difficulties and pressures such as difficulties in studying; difficulties in relationships with friends, teachers and family; difficulties in career orientation; difficulties in adapting to changes in the body (fpt.edu.vn, 2022)

High school students in Hanoi are quite large in number, including students with registered residence in Hanoi and students from other provinces, studying in a competitive environment, with rich and diverse entertainment conditions. With the common characteristics of high school students, H'Mong high school students have their own characteristics of ethnic minorities. The H'Mong ethnic group resides in most of the northern mountainous provinces in a fairly large area, along the Vietnam - China and Vietnam - Laos borders from Lang Son to Nghe An, mainly concentrated in the provinces of the East and Northwest of Vietnam such as: Ha Giang, Lao Cai, Lai Chau, Son La... Due to nomadic habits, some H'Mong people in the 1980s and 1990s migrated to the Central Highlands, living scattered in some places in Gia Lai and Kon Tum.

The study will compare the similarities and differences in the learning and entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi with those of the H'Mong ethnic group, thereby providing some exchanges and discussions with educators, businesses/entertainment service providers to have appropriate strategies to target this specific group.

Research Method

To serve the research, the group of authors used two methods including desk research (reviewing documents published in the media) and conducting a sociological survey (collecting questionnaires from students living and studying in Hanoi and areas where H'Mong people reside). The data will be compiled and analyzed using Excel software.

Using desk research methods, the authors reviewed documents on characteristics of high school students, statistics on high school students in Hanoi and areas where H'Mong people live, and documents on the learning and entertainment needs of high school students in the two areas above.

The group of authors developed a survey form to conduct a sociological investigation, with questions about:

1. Evaluate the program being studied;
2. The group of subjects being taught at the school is not yet focused on;
3. Extracurricular activities/life skills dissemination;
4. What subjects are you interested in?
5. Intentions after finishing high school;
6. Support and help from people around with studying;
7. Assess individual entertainment needs;
8. Choose the form, means, place, and with whom you entertain;
9. Finance for entertainment;
10. Evaluate the entertainment services in the area;
11. How to balance between learning needs and entertainment needs

The data collection method was conducted by the research team based on the convenience sampling method. The survey was built on Google drive, conducted via the link: <https://forms.gle/L345ysV1YZPRWYkJ6> (for survey subjects in areas where H'Mong people live); <https://forms.gle/a7Q4DBjXKbcXvQVg6> (for survey subjects in Hanoi) through social media such as: Facebook, Zalo, Email... and also directly distributed the questionnaire. The total number of questionnaires collected was 111. The survey data was compiled and statistically analyzed using Excel software, from which it was analyzed and demonstrated the research problem. Each question has answers for the survey subjects to choose from (one answer or multiple answers or choose 1 level/5-level Likert scale). The research team collected survey data and used it to analyze, compare, and illustrate the content of the article.

Figure 1. Statistics on Age of Survey Subjects (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

The majority of the survey subjects were 17 years old in Hanoi, while the majority were 16 years old in the H'Mong ethnic minority area.

Figure 2. Statistics on Ethnicity of Survey Subjects (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

Thus, the survey subjects in the H'Mong ethnic living area are all H'Mong ethnic people, while in Hanoi, 98% are Kinh ethnic people.

Figure 3. Statistics on the Level of Survey Subjects (Unit: %)
 Source: Survey results

The survey subjects in Hanoi were mainly 11th grade students (60.4%), while in the H'Mong ethnic living area, 10th grade students accounted for half (50%).

In addition, the survey results will be integrated by the author team and used as analytical evidence in the content of the article below.

Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

Concept of Demand

Needs have long been the subject of research in most branches of biological and social sciences. In the field of socio-economics, the issue of needs is found in the research of famous scientists such as Jeremy Bentham, Benfield, William Stanley Jevons, John Ramsay McCulloch, Edward S. Herman. It is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon, characteristic of all living things. The presence of needs in any living thing, even in any society considered as a complex living body, is a characteristic to distinguish that subject from the surrounding environment.

Until now there has not been a common definition for the concept of demand.

Need is understood as the necessity of something. But “something” is only the external expression of the need. Behind the expression lies the essence of the need which can be temporarily called necessity. The need being discussed can be considered the expression of another more fundamental need. Thus, the concepts of need and necessity are relative to each other. That shows that the needs of a living organism are a complex, multi-layered system, including countless chains of expressions and needs that are intricately linked, capable of development and diversification. However, for easy identification, the simplest separate need is made up of a necessity and a form of expression.

A certain form of expression is concretized into the object of a certain need. The object of a need is what the need is directed towards and can satisfy that need. One object can satisfy several needs, one need can be satisfied by several objects, in which the level of satisfaction is different.

Characteristics of Needs

Needs are a psychological phenomenon of humans; they are demands, desires, and aspirations of humans regarding material and spiritual matters in order to survive and develop. Depending on the level of awareness, living environment, and psychological and physiological characteristics, each person has different needs.

A need is a feeling of lack of something that a person feels.

Needs are the factors that motivate people to act. The more urgent the need, the more it can control people. In terms of management, controlling needs means being able to control individuals (in this case, awareness has a certain influence: high awareness will have the ability to restrain the satisfaction of needs).

The needs of an individual are diverse and endless. In terms of management, the manager only controls those needs that are related to the individual's work efficiency. Satisfying a certain need of an individual simultaneously creates another need according to the manager's direction, so the manager can always control the individuals.

Needs are the characteristics of a living organism, expressing the state of deficiency or imbalance of that individual and thus distinguishing it from the living environment. Minimum needs, also known as necessities, have been programmed through a very long process of existence, development and evolution.

Needs strongly influence psychological life in general and human behavior in particular. Needs are of interest to many scientific fields, studied and used in many different areas of life and society.

Thus, the needs have the following basic characteristics:

- Demand is often variable and unstable.
- Needs are often complex and have many levels.
- Demand often depends on many factors.

Types of Needs

Aristotle argued that humans have two main types of needs: physical and spiritual. This classification is largely arbitrary but it has influenced us to this day, and we are accustomed to dividing needs into "physical needs" and "spiritual needs".

The focus of scientists is the arrangement of needs in a hierarchical structure. The idea of the hierarchy of needs began to emerge at the beginning of the last century. Benfield writes: "The first view of the theory of needs said that the satisfaction of a need at a lower level in the hierarchy of needs will give rise to the desire to satisfy a need at a higher level". Among the modern research works can be mentioned the results of such classifications as K. Alderfer: existence, relationship, growth (1969); D. McClelland: achievement, affiliation, power (1987); V. Podmarcov: guarantee, tendency, prestige; V. Tarasenko: existence, development.

Psychologist Abraham Maslow proposed the basic human needs expressed through the pyramid of needs as follows:

Figure 4. Maslow's hierarchy of needs
Source: <https://www.bitesizelearning.co.uk/>.

Maslow's proposal in the 1940s-1950s introduced a hierarchy of needs to describe basic human needs from basic to high level:

Physiological needs: These are the most basic human needs, including the needs for food, water, sleep, reproduction and other survival needs.

Safety needs: After physiological needs are met, people have the need to feel safe and secure. This includes the need for physical security, job security, financial security, stability and protection.

Social needs: Once basic needs are met, people have needs for social and emotional interaction. These are the needs for love, friendship, family, community and social relationships.

Status and self-esteem needs: When people feel secure and have stable social relationships, the need for personal growth, work and career advancement becomes important. These are the needs for success, work appreciation and personal growth.

Self-actualization needs: This is the highest level in Maslow's hierarchy of needs. When basic needs and job needs are met, people have the need to seek self-expression and explore personal potential.

According to Maslow, people will focus on satisfying lower-level needs before moving on to higher levels in the hierarchy of needs.

For businesses, they are interested in the need for payment, that is, the need for payment in money, also known as demand. That is the need for goods and services limited by the ability to pay in money or other payment assets of the population (people) and society (organizations, state agencies, unions, businesses, etc.)

Literature Review

The need for learning and the need for entertainment are part of human needs in general. In educating and developing people, it is impossible not to study these two types of needs.

What are learning needs?

Learning needs are an inevitable and objective requirement of learners in life and activities. It represents the necessity of learning something and is satisfied to develop knowledge, skills and abilities.

Learning needs are expressed through activities:

- Realize that learning is for self-development and advancement in life.
- Desire to grasp new knowledge, improve skills and develop yourself
- Learn from the surrounding environment to develop yourself and promote personal success
- Actively seek out information sources, seek out mentors, or participate in educational activities
- Set learning goals

The need for learning plays an important role in the development of an individual, improving physical and mental quality, bringing health, wealth and status to people in the future. Specifically, the need for learning helps people:

- Explore and acquire knowledge
- Personal skill development
- Expand job opportunities
- Self-development and self-confidence
- Communication and social interaction

Thus, when people have the need to learn, it will create motivation and dedication to help acquire new knowledge and achieve success in life and work.

What are entertainment needs?

The need for rest and entertainment is formed in the process of socio-economic development under the influence of objective factors of the external environment, which first of all depends on the method of social production, more specifically, the need for people to restore health - the ability to work, physical and mental health lost in the process of living and working. In other words, the need to appreciate beauty and entertainment is aroused by the special influence of the living, studying and working environment in industrial civilization. Stress has made it necessary for people to seek rest, entertainment, meetings, oblivion, liberation to return to nature and the self.

Entertainment needs can include: pure entertainment needs and special entertainment needs.

Pure entertainment needs are a form of human needs that require rest and relaxation to make the mind free and comfortable - to do things that they love or participate in forms of entertainment that are mainly spiritual in nature and not heavy on physical exercise - to help people escape from stress and fatigue, relieve psychological stress, depression, sadness and discomfort or simply seek joy, comfort and peace of mind by participating in spiritual entertainment activities such as going to concerts, theaters, exhibitions, fairs, shopping, etc.

Or it is the need to satisfy a passionate interest or hobby that helps people relieve fatigue and boredom, bringing mental relaxation through heavy physical activities such as participating in sports games such as surfing, skiing, mountain climbing, bowling, tennis... or enthusiastically participating in exciting games.

The need for special entertainment is a type of need that requires a high level of exploration of the cognitive world, expanding understanding, improving knowledge about the world and everything around it, about everything that humans have not yet known, with the desire to learn deeply to have extensive knowledge - for example, the most unique features of natural landscapes, historical culture, customs, religious beliefs, wonders, unique architectural works... of countries and peoples in the world ; or interesting things about science, cinema, technology...

However, it is impossible to separate the need for pure entertainment from the need for special entertainment. But basically, the need for pure entertainment does not require too deep understanding or too heavy mental activity.

Analyze the Similarities and Differences in the Learning and Entertainment Needs of High School Students in Hanoi with Those of H'Mong High School Students

Overview of High School Students in Hanoi with H'Mong High School Students

Overview of high school students

High school students are an important group of learners in the education system in Vietnam. High school students are at an important stage in their lives. To ensure an effective learning process and a bright future for them, it is necessary to pay attention to the basic characteristics of high school students. These characteristics include:

1. *Age and stage of development:* High school students are between 15 and 18 years old, which is an important stage of psychological and physical development. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize educational orientation, life skills training and physical development for students during these years.

2. *Learning Needs:* High school students have an increasing need to learn, especially in today's competitive job market. Therefore, schools and families need to provide learning programs that are appropriate to each student's vision and goals.

3. *Independence and maturity:* High school students are more independent and mature than middle school students and need to be empowered and responsible for their studies and time management. However,

to achieve this autonomy, they need to be equipped with self-management and self-discipline skills to become smart and responsible learners. (xaydungso.vn, 2024)

High school students today in modern society have some limitations such as:

- In some young people, revolutionary sentiment and spirit are still weak, and their level of social awareness is low. They have an attitude of disdain for manual labor, preferring to live a lavish, wasteful life, showing off, and having fun...
- Youth is the age of dreams, thirst for creativity, likes new things, and prefers physical beauty, so it is easy for superficial beauty to sway their will, and they forget the old when they have something new...
- Young people are very enthusiastic in their work, very optimistic and love life but also easily pessimistic and discouraged when they fail.
- Youth is the age of developing talent, absorbing new things quickly, very intelligent and creative but also easily becomes subjective, rash, arrogant and reluctant to learn thoroughly to improve their level. They like to focus on the future, pay little attention to the present and easily forget the past. (thpttaytienhai.thaibinh.edu.vn, 2013)

Overview of high school students in Hanoi

Hanoi is the capital, considered the cradle of culture and education of the country. Hanoi has the largest educational scale in the country with 2,875 schools and 2.3 million preschool and primary school students. Along with that, the capital also has about 1 million students from 120 universities and colleges studying and living. (kinhtedothi.vn, 2024).

Currently, in Hanoi, there are 119 public high schools, 101 private high schools and some other types such as autonomous public schools, jointly managed public schools, vocational education centers, continuing education centers, international schools (Hanoi Department of Education and Training, 2024).

Figure 5. High School System in Hanoi by the End of 2023

Source: Hanoi Department of Education and Training

Regarding the scale of public high schools (excluding autonomous public high schools and jointly managed public high schools): by the 2024-2025 school year, Hanoi is expected to have about 121 schools (an increase of 2 schools compared to the 2023-2024 school year); by the 2025-2026 school year, there will be about 123 schools; by the 2026-2027 school year, there will be about 125 schools. And corresponding to the number of schools, the number of high school students in Hanoi is currently about more than 400,000 students studying at schools.

High school students in Hanoi have the following characteristics:

- + relatively large number,
- + early exposure to modern society,
- + Most of them are very interested and invested in their education by their parents,
- + have many dreams, ambitions and aspirations,
- + bear a lot of pressure

Overview of H'Mong high school students

About 4-5 thousand years ago, the H'Mong and Dao people were both pushed out of the Tam Mieu region in China by the Han people and had to endure wars and migrations that lasted for thousands of years. In the late 17th and early 18th centuries, they began to migrate to Southeast Asia. Based on the color, characteristics of costumes and pronunciation, the H'Mong people in Vietnam are divided into 4 local groups: White H'Mong, Black H'Mong, Green H'Mong and Flower H'Mong. The H'Mong people live mainly in the provinces of Ha Giang, Son La, Dien Bien, Lao Cai, Lai Chau, Yen Bai, Thanh Hoa, Nghe An, Dak Lak, Dak Nong... Currently, the H'Mong people have migrated to many other places such as Cao Bang, Bac Kan, Lam Dong. (nhandan.vn, 2022)

Currently, H'Mong high school students mainly study at ethnic boarding high schools in provinces such as Ha Giang (3 schools), Son La (11 schools), Lao Cai (9 schools), Lai Chau (14 schools) ...

Characteristics of ethnic minority high school students in general and H'Mong high school students in particular are as follows:

- + small quantity
- + limited service material conditions
- + not much attention from parents about studying
- + limited vision
- + the will to strive to escape poverty and become rich is also relatively high

Before considering the similarities and comparing the differences in learning needs and entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi and H'Mong high school students, according to the survey results, in general, the students surveyed have a balance between learning needs and entertainment needs. 40% of H'Mong high school students and 59.4% of high school students in Hanoi assessed that learning needs balance entertainment needs.

Figure 6. Statistics on the Balance between Learning Needs and Entertainment Needs
Source: Survey results

The Actual Similarities and Differences in Learning Needs of High School Students in Hanoi with High School Students of the H'Mong Ethnic Group

Similarities in learning needs of high school students in Hanoi with high school students of H'Mong ethnic group

First: Regarding awareness of learning needs

Through the survey, the authors found that there is a very high similarity between high school students in Hanoi and high school students of the H'mong ethnic group: all students intend to complete 3 years of high school (100% chose).

Besides, with their learning experience, high school students in both areas rated the program they are studying at average and difficult levels.

Figure 7. Evaluation Statistics of the Program Being Studied (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

Such awareness of the curriculum makes students more conscious of studying and certainly the knowledge they acquire will be of great help in the future.

Second: Set learning goals

Learning goals are a manifestation of learning needs, a very important orientation, and also a driving force for each student, especially high school students about to enter the threshold of life.

When asked about career orientation or plans while in high school, the survey results were as follows:

Figure 8. Statistics on Having/Not Having Orientation or Planning for Future Career while in High School (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

Thus, there is a great similarity between high school students in Hanoi and H'Mong high school students in that the majority (over 70%) of students have an orientation or plan for their future career when they are in high school.

One very good thing is that the learning needs of students in both areas are supported and assisted in their studies by their families, teachers, and friends.

Figure 9. Statistics on Support and Assistance for Studying from Family, Teachers, and Friends Around (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

For high school students in Hanoi, the support and help they receive in studying from their families, teachers and friends (97% claimed yes) is similar to that of H'Mong high school students (90% claimed yes).

The goal after graduating from high school of students may be to continue studying at a higher level or to work, or some of you have not yet determined. However, the number of surveyed opinions that will continue to study at university is very large (>50%).

Figure 10. Statistics on Study and Employment Orientation after Graduation High School Graduate (Unit: %)

Source: Survey results

It can be seen that after graduating from high school, students in Hanoi have a very high rate of choosing to continue studying at university out of the total number of orientation choices (77.2%). The choices of H'Mong high school students are very diverse: studying at university, college, working in agriculture and studying at university, doing online business combined with studying at university, in which there is also a similarity that the rate of choosing to study at university is 50%.

In addition, it is encouraging that 19.8% of high school students in Hanoi choose to study abroad after graduating from high school, and this rate of H'Mong high school students is 10%. Thus, the need to study in a foreign environment of these students is similar and proves that they want to study in a place with differences in language, culture and a higher level of economic development.

Difference in the learning needs of high school students in Hanoi with high school students of H'Mong ethnic group:

First: Access to teachers and curriculum

Learning needs are influenced by many factors, creating differences between different subjects. The very basic factors are teachers and curriculum will affect the learning needs of students.

The teaching and learning process is a social process closely linked to human activities. If the teaching and learning process is considered a system, then the relationship between the teacher's teaching activities and the students' learning activities is essentially a inter-dependent relationship. Teachers, on the basis of organizing students to master knowledge, skills, techniques, and develop cognitive abilities, form for them a scientific worldview, moral qualities in particular, and personality development in general according to the proposed educational goals.

In the teaching process, stimulating students' learning needs is very necessary. Teachers need to acknowledge and encourage. Recognition and encouragement are related to the fourth need - the need for respect. The content of this need includes two types: Self-esteem and respect from others. Self-esteem includes the desire to gain trust, to be capable, to have courage, to have achievements, to be independent, confident, free, to grow up, to express oneself and to improve oneself. The second type is the need to be respected by others. Respect is to be respected and admired by others. It is the ability to gain prestige, to be recognized, to be recognized, to be encouraged, to have status, to have honor, etc. In work or life, when a person is encouraged and recognized for their work achievements, they are willing to work more enthusiastically and more effectively. For learners, meeting and achieving this need can make students study more actively and try harder (philology.hpu2.edu.vn, 2015).

In addition to improving the professional quality of teachers, the Hanoi education sector has organized many emulation movements and awards to encourage teachers to promote their creativity, creating liveliness and attractiveness for each lesson. Typical examples include the movements "Building a Cultural School - Exemplary Teachers - Elegant Students", "Teacher - Kind Mother", "Discipline, Sympathy, Responsibility"; "Hanoi Teachers Sponsoring Poor Students", especially the awards "Dedicated and Creative Hanoi Teachers", "Innovation and Creativity in Teaching and Learning", creating a vibrant competitive atmosphere throughout the sector, contributing to improving the quality of teaching and learning. (tapchicongsan.org.vn, 2021)

In 2023, Hanoi successfully organized the first High School Band Festival for the first time, receiving enthusiastic response from schools and a large number of students. In order to enhance aesthetic education, political ideology, ethics, lifestyle, and behavioral culture in the educational environment, and improve the spiritual and cultural life of students, in 2024, the Hanoi Department of Education and Training will organize the first High School Choir Festival. (kinhtedothi.vn, 2024)

However, the number of high school teachers in Hanoi is lacking. According to the Hanoi People's Committee, in the 2023-2024 school year, 33 new public kindergartens and general schools were established and put into operation in the city with a scale of 554 classes and 19,350 students. Meanwhile, the number of educational staff is 16,004 people short of the norm set by the Ministry of Education and Training.

In the 2023-2024 school year, the city proposed to be assigned an additional 8,939 positions in the education sector. The Central Organizing Committee decided to announce the addition of 2,648 positions to Hanoi city, including: Preschool positions (191 people), primary school positions (977 people), junior high school positions (1,033 people), high school positions (447 people). (tienphong.vn, 2024)

Thus, high school students in Hanoi have the opportunity to access quality teachers, thereby increasing their learning needs.

Meanwhile, for ethnic minority students in general and the H'Mong ethnic group in particular, from the difficulties in living and studying conditions, it is recognized that a part of students lack confidence, self-reliance, are afraid of difficulties, have a shy mentality, have an inferiority complex, and have difficulty integrating when going to school. While entering the high school environment requires independence, creativity, and initiative in both studying and living..., students feel anxious, live in isolation, and are afraid to communicate with teachers and friends. Another obstacle that teachers at the Ethnic Minority High School themselves acknowledge is limited communication between teachers and students. Students come from many ethnic groups such as Thai, Mong, Kho Mu... with their own languages and cultures; play and live according to different ethnic groups. Although they still use Kinh to talk to teachers and friends, there is still a gap. That requires teachers and schools to proactively approach and communicate so that students are more open, thereby improving the effectiveness of teaching and educating life skills and boarding management. (giaoducthoidai.vn , 2023)

Another difference is the curriculum of students in Hanoi and H'Mong students.

Figure 11. Statistics on Subjects that are Not Given Attention at School
 Source: *Survey results*

According to a survey of students in Hanoi, the schools they are studying at are not paying the most attention to the group of arts (63.4% of opinions), while H'Mong students think that the group of natural sciences is the least focused on (80% of opinions). Thus, from the comments about the group of subjects that are not focused on, it shows the difference in the needs and desires of Hanoi students to study arts, while H'Mong students have the need to study natural sciences.

Second: Surrounding environment

The very basic condition to generate and satisfy the learning needs of high school students is the surrounding environment, including the family, social, school and classroom environments.

In Hanoi, the city's goal is to create all conditions for students who wish to attend high school. However, to ensure the division of students, students who do not want to attend high school can attend vocational colleges or continuing education centers. The department's leaders also affirmed that in addition to studying culture, students can study vocational training, and that they are not required to study high

school, but also absolutely prohibit schools and education departments from not allowing students with poor academic performance to take the 10th grade entrance exam for high school because of their achievements, which is contrary to their rights. The Hanoi Department of Education and Training will also limit educational institutions, facilities and teaching staff that do not meet the standards and will not even assign quotas to institutions that do not meet the material conditions. Therefore, non-public schools must improve the quality of education and build good facilities so that Hanoi students can study in the best environment. (qdnd.vn, 2016)

In some high schools, such as Phu Xuyen A High School, Phu Xuyen District, to promote quality, the school has increased inspection and supervision of teaching and learning; increased observation periods, encouraged and motivated teachers to be enthusiastic and dedicated to their profession. Students are required to put all electronic devices in the cabinet until the end of class to focus on their lessons.

Through the high school graduation mock exams, the school announced the results, rewarded good students and praised those who had made more progress than before, creating a competitive learning movement. Weak students were tutored and supplemented by teachers for free. After one year of study, the percentage of students with university entrance scores was exceptionally high.

At Phan Huy Chu High School in Dong Da District, the school's solution is to have periodic centralized tests every year, and students with low scores are put into remedial classes. There were initially many students in this group, but they all made an effort to withdraw from that class. The way to encourage them to try is to get high scores and be promptly rewarded by the school. (tienphong.vn, 2024)

However, in areas where the Hmong ethnic group lives, there are barriers to education in ethnic minority and mountainous areas, which also affects the learning needs of Hmong students.

Part of the reason comes from the fact that their families are poor, their parents are busy with work and therefore do not really pay attention to and encourage their children to study. Growing up in such circumstances, many children do not clearly realize the importance of studying, so they neglect and spend their time playing. In addition, most students have to go to school far away from home, lacking daily care and attention from their parents...

100% of the students are Mong, Dao, Muong, Tay, Phu La... ethnic groups living in remote, extremely difficult areas. Therefore, the level of awareness, life skills, communication skills... of the students and their families are still limited. In particular, in the community there are still bad customs that affect the awareness, lifestyle, and culture of students such as wife-catching, early marriage...

In families, awareness of “literacy” is not high, leaving the children’s education to the school. Even the situation of students dropping out of school is quite common. The combination between school and family to educate and care for students faces many limitations.

Students stay at school for weeks, even months, before returning home, so teachers, in addition to teaching, also have the responsibility of managing and taking care of students. Teachers have accompanied and cared for many generations of students in terms of food, clothing, style, and living habits...

In class, teachers are teachers, but after the school bell rings, they become the second parents of their students, so the workload and pressure of responsibility are much heavier and greater. However, when choosing to stick with teaching at boarding schools, teachers all try to fulfill their abilities and responsibilities so that their students receive the best. (Giaoducthoidai, 2023)

According to the survey, high school students in Hanoi have more opportunities to participate in extracurricular activities/life skills training, that is 75.2% of the surveyed students participated in career guidance classes, while 70% of the surveyed students who are H’Mong high school students said that they did not have access to extracurricular activities.

Figure 12. Statistics on Extracurricular Activities/Life Skills Dissemination for High School Students
 Source: Survey results

Third: Ability to self-study and desire for self-improvement

Students' learning needs will be the source of motivation for self-learning ability and desire for self-improvement.

According to Knowles (1975): "Self-learning describes a process in which individuals take the initiative, with or without the help of others, in identifying their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, selecting and implementing learning strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes appropriately". Self-learning ability includes the following components: (1) Self-identifying the need for self-learning (or having the need for self-learning) means having the desire, motivation to learn, and wanting to enjoy the learning process; (2) Self-determination of learning goals includes external goals (mandatory and internal goals (voluntary, self-aware, needs); (3) Self-determination of resources is to consider "environmental factors that play a decisive role in self-study such as: learning resources, learning support and learning context"; (4) Self-determination of learning strategies: Self-determination of learning strategies includes self-determination of learning goals, objectives and tasks; self-determination of learning methods (in class, at home); self-determination of schedules (time to study compulsory knowledge, time to explore and discover on your own, time for daily activities); (5) Self-assessment includes self-assessment of the learning process (process assessment/regular assessment), self-assessment of how learning is going? What is your current learning method? What knowledge is being focused on? What are the goals being set? (Education Magazine, 2021).

In the Vietnam's National Human Resource Development Strategy, the capacity for autonomy and career orientation of high school students is an important content. Accordingly, educational methods must attach importance to fostering the capacity for self-study and self-research, creating conditions for learners to develop creative thinking, practice practical skills, participate in research and experiments...

High school students are the youth union members of the country. However, in reality, high school students face many difficulties in promoting their ability to be autonomous in studying and choosing a career in the face of social fluctuations. (<http://vjst.vn/>, 2021)

High school students in Hanoi are currently equipped by their families and schools with facilities and means for self-study. Companies, IT centers, and learning centers in Hanoi also provide many online courses with the help of AI, convenient applications, so high school students can study effectively. Meanwhile, due to economic conditions not being equal to those in the capital Hanoi, H'Mong high school students do not have many conditions to study by themselves, perhaps because they have to take care of their families' finances or their families do not invest in equipment and means for studying and self-study.

In addition, for Hmong students at ethnic boarding high schools, the input quality of cultural subjects is still low and uneven. Students' reading comprehension, calculation, self-study, exchange, sharing, and pair and group learning skills are not good; their spirit, will and desire to learn are also not high. (giaoducthoidai.vn, 2023)

Box 1: Some applications that can support students in effective self-study

Evernote: This is a note management application that helps students organize information, store notes and important documents.

Quizlet: This application helps students create and review with tests, flashcards and information cards.

Khan Academy: An online teaching platform with thousands of lectures on many topics, from mathematics to history and linguistics.

Coursera and edX: Provide online courses from the world's leading universities and educational institutions.

ChatGPT: A virtual assistant that can answer questions and provide information on many topics.

Google Classroom: This application helps students create and manage assignments, tests, and exchange assignments with friends and teachers.

Duolingo: This application helps students learn foreign languages in a fun and effective way.

Source: <https://giaoducthoidai.vn/>, 2023

According to the survey, during their studies at high schools, students in Hanoi and the H'Mong people also showed different interests in subjects. While students in Hanoi were interested in social sciences (46.5%), H'Mong students were most interested in natural sciences (70%), which shows that high school students in Hanoi have the desire and need to study more social sciences and H'Mong high school students have the need to study more natural sciences.

Figure 13. Statistics on Interesting Subjects
Source: Survey results

The reality of similarities and differences in entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi and high school students of the H'Mong ethnic group

Similarities in entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi with high school students of the H'Mong ethnic group

Through the survey, it was found that both high school students in Hanoi and high school students of the H'Mong ethnic group have entertainment needs at an average level (level 3 on the 5-level scale).

Figure 14. Statistics on Individual Entertainment Needs
Source: Survey results

Besides, the place that high school students in Hanoi and H'Mong people choose for entertainment is almost always at home, through the means of phones, computers and technological devices.

Figure 15. Statistics on Forms, Means and Places for Entertainment
Source: Survey results

83.2% of Hanoi high school students surveyed chose to stay at home and 90% of H'Mong high school students chose to stay at home for entertainment, this rate is very high, proving that the family environment is still very important and safe, comfortable and economical for students. Modern means are now very popular, 92.1% of high school students in Hanoi and 70% of H'Mong students surveyed chose phones, computers and technology devices for entertainment. This is a huge similarity between these two groups.

The educational process takes place through schools and through life experiences. High school students will not only learn in class but also have relaxation and entertainment in art classes, physical education, class activities, and flag salutes at the beginning of the week. According to the survey results in Chart 9, high school students in Hanoi are very interested in art subjects (37.6%), but only 20% of H'Mong students are interested in art subjects. However, according to the survey, according to Chart 7, art subjects are not currently being given attention by schools, 63.4% of the survey subjects in Hanoi and 70% of the survey subjects in the H'Mong ethnic minority area assessed that art subjects are not being given attention by their schools. This shows that the need for entertainment for high school students in both areas is very large.

Difference in the entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi with high school students of the H'Mong ethnic group

After hours of studying and working hard, people need to rest.

Rest and relax to regain strength and spirit. To meet that need, it is necessary to create many playgrounds suitable for all subjects and ages. Currently, entertainment technology is quite rich such as: audio-visual, participation in cultural activities, sports, television playgrounds, competitions, electronic games, etc. However, in the context of limited land, crowded population, every inch of land is worth an inch of gold, there is still a lack of places for entertainment, especially in rural areas, mountainous areas, remote areas and even industrial zones. Public opinion is upset and mentions a lot about the lack of places for children to play. Along with the creation of playgrounds, many issues that society is concerned about arise, such as how entertainment can benefit people. Reality shows that there are many cases of entertainment harming people. Children play too many electronic games leading to addiction, which negatively affects their studies and health. (nhandan.vn, 2012)

High school students are characterized by their young age, vibrant personality and lots of energy. According to education experts, being able to play to their fullest and do what they like not only creates excitement for students to study better but also helps them reduce the stress of studying, taking exams as well as the expectations that their parents place on them. However, due to regional characteristics, according to the survey of the research team, the entertainment needs of students in Hanoi and H'Mong students have some differences in terms of entertainment needs, entertainment partners, entertainment locations, and financial resources for entertainment..

According to Chart 10, we see that high school students in Hanoi have a high level of entertainment needs, accounting for 40.6%, while only 10% of H'Mong high school students have a high level of entertainment needs.

Chart 11 also shows us that H'Mong high school students choose to have entertainment at local cultural and sports centers, up to 50% of the survey respondents choose, but only 8.9% of high school students in Hanoi choose to have entertainment at this location. Up to 54.5% of high school students in Hanoi choose to travel for entertainment, while only 10% of H'Mong high school students choose to have entertainment by traveling. And according to the survey statistics in Chart 11, 60% of H'Mong high school students but only 35.6% of high school students in Hanoi rate the entertainment services in the place of residence as very diverse.

And those entertainment services have almost fully satisfied the entertainment needs of H'Mong high school students (90% of the survey respondents answered yes) while only 1% of high school students in Hanoi are satisfied with the entertainment services where they live.

According to the survey, high school students in Hanoi choose to entertain themselves a lot (75.2%) while 100% of H'Mong high school students choose to entertain with friends. Perhaps because H'Mong high school students spend a lot of time at ethnic boarding schools, friends are still the ones who share more when entertaining.

Figure 16. Statistical Assessment of the Diversity of Entertainment Services in Residential Areas
 Source: Survey results

Figure 17. Statistics on Entertainment Audiences
 Source: Survey results

To satisfy the entertainment needs, high school students who are still dependent still receive financial support from their parents. While 90% of the surveyed subjects are H'Mong high school students who receive 100,000 - 300,000 VND/month for entertainment needs, 10% do not receive support, only 30.7% of students in Hanoi receive 100,000 - 300,000 VND/month, the remaining high school students in Hanoi are given a higher level of 300,000 - 500,000 VND/month (25.7%) or 500,000 - 700,000 VND/month (14.9%), 700,00 - 1,000,000 VND/month (10.9%). This shows that high school students in Hanoi will receive more support to satisfy their entertainment needs than H'Mong high school students.

Figure 18. Statistics on the Amount of Money Parents Provide for Entertainment Needs
 Source: Survey results

In general, high school students in Hanoi and H'Mong high school students have great similarities in their learning needs and entertainment needs, but there are also specific differences in each need.

Conclusion

After researching, evaluating and surveying the similarities and differences in learning needs and entertainment needs of high school students in Hanoi and H'Mong high school students, the group of authors has some discussions and suggestions:

First: For high schools and families of high school students in Hanoi and the areas where the H'Mong people live.

Schools need to pay attention to the learning and entertainment needs of students. It is necessary to increase the teaching of subjects such as art, life skills, and self-defense so that students are truly interested in learning and relaxing, reducing pressure, discovering and developing the hidden abilities of high school students in both areas.

It is important to create conditions in terms of facilities and technical infrastructure so that high school students truly consider school as a place to create excitement and joy, thereby promoting the need to learn and satisfying the entertainment needs of students.

It is suggested that schools improve the quality of education by improving the qualifications of high school teachers, increasing income and encouraging and motivating teachers to teach in remote areas, specifically areas where the H'Mong people live and study.

As for families, in general, parents need to spend more time understanding their children's learning needs and entertaining and relaxing with them, and should not expect or put too much pressure on their children. For families with H'Mong high school students, they should provide additional financial resources so that their children can satisfy their entertainment needs, increase their awareness and access to modern life.

Second: For high school students in Hanoi and high school students of H'Mong ethnic group

Students need to realize that high school is a very important time and not long, so they need to improve their self-study ability, balance time and money for studying and entertainment. During their high school

years, they need to take advantage of learning opportunities as well as career guidance, subjects that are focused on teaching at school to create a foundation to continue writing their dreams. They also need to spend time talking, relaxing and entertaining with their families, connecting with their parents to have valuable moments and advice.

High school students in Hanoi live in a better environment than H'Mong high school students, but that also presents challenges and pitfalls. Therefore, students need to be vigilant, raise their awareness of studying, and stay away from harmful entertainment and unhealthy entertainment venues.

Third: With local authorities and entertainment service providers

Local authorities need to create conditions for education development as well as build appropriate cultural, sports and entertainment facilities to attract high school students after stressful school hours. This requires the coordination of many agencies from the central to local levels and the provision of adequate resources.

Entertainment service providers need to diversify healthy forms of entertainment, and can also cooperate with high schools to create playgrounds right in class to provide knowledge and relaxation, stimulate learning needs, and satisfy entertainment needs of high school students.

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